

Life cycle check of LED street lighting

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ABSTRACT

With the present debate on the climate and the effects man made products have on the environment, the new products made possible by the currently emerging nano-technologies give raise to questions on their safety, their potential new environmental impacts, and the legitimacy of the problems for which they offer solutions.

A light-application area, whose history to some extent documents the development in lighting technologies, is the lighting facilities that illuminate our infrastructures. In Denmark, it is up to the local municipality to decide which type of street lamps they need for their streets and many are considering light-emitting diode (LED) lamps as an alternative to ordinary metal halogen lamps.

The network and actors influencing the role of LED street lighting in Denmark is investigated in this report to trace if there are any emerging irreversibility, and if there signs of a stabilization in the network around LED street lighting in Denmark.

To investigate the environmental impact that the choice of street lamp may have, we have conducted a life cycle check (LCC) on an LED street lighting solution called Cobra Medium and compared it to a metal halogen lamp. Our LCC reveals that the bulb is the optimal part to optimize in street lighting, since the electricity used for lighting accounts for 95% of the total energy consumption in its lifespan of 40 years, also considering the production of the pole and housing. The total energy consumption of LED street lighting is determined to be 37% lower than for a standard metal halogen lamp.

Figure 1: Actor-network diagram of the actors influencing the role of LED street lighting in Danish municipalities.